

SIG-CM 2019: Workshop on Conceptual Modeling Report

Nicholas Weber
University of Washington
Seattle, WA
nmweber@uw.edu

Katrina Fenlon
University of Maryland
College Park, MD
kfenlon@umd.edu

Andrea K. Thomer
University of Michigan
Ann Arbor, MI
athomer@umich.edu

Peter Organisciak
University of Denver
Denver, CO
porganis@du.edu

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Abstract

The first meeting of the Special Interest Group on Conceptual Modeling (June 6, 2019) convened an international, interdisciplinary group of scholars that work in the organization and representation of information. Presenters shared emerging issues in the field, and attendees developing an agenda for conceptual modeling research needs into the future. This report summarizes presentations and discussions from the workshop.

Keywords: information science; information representation; conceptual modeling.

1 Introduction

Conceptual models often provide formal representation information and identity conditions necessary for the organization, retrieval, and publication of digital resources. As such, conceptual modeling has a rich intellectual tradition within information science where such activities are fundamental to both theoretical and practical work. Notable examples include the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR), data models from the semantic web, like the Resource Description Framework (RDF), as well as the development of protocols unique to the exchange of digital objects, such as the Open Archives Initiative for Object Reuse and Exchange (OAI-ORE). We believe that sustaining this rich tradition of research and development in conceptual modeling requires renewed efforts from the digital library and information science community. Many of the protocols, data models, and descriptive frameworks described above are in need of update, revision, or extension to remain useful in contemporary computing environments. At the same time we also recognize that new and emerging information technologies will require fundamentally new conceptual models. At the 2019 Joint Conference for Digital Libraries, the SIG-CM (Special Interest Group on Conceptual Modeling) workshop convened a group of researchers and practitioners interested in developing a collaborative research agenda around conceptual modeling for information science. This workshop focused on presenting and discussing participants' ongoing research, as well as a number of broad discussions about persistent challenges and future research directions in conceptual

modelling. The goal of the workshop was to develop a scholarly community that can collectively advance research into information standards, protocols, schemas, data models, and information architectures as first-class research objects. This report summarizes the presentations and discussion at the 2019 JCDL workshop. The summaries, current challenges, and future directions described below should be read as an initial step towards that goal.

2 Keynote

2.1 The role of conceptual modeling information science

Karen Wickett.

Karen Wickett gave the inaugural keynote of SIG-CM, entitled “The role of conceptual modeling information science”. In it, she built on Bates’s notion of information science as meta-science, in particular the observation that practitioners in information science have a “knack for operating at the level of representation of [a] subject matter.” It would seem that representations and levels of representation are core to research and practice in information science, and conceptual modeling is a method that is directly attuned to issues of representation. Wickett identified some “fundamental questions” that drive conceptual modeling in information science, and discussed the morning’s workshop presentations in the context of those fundamental questions. Wickett posed conceptual modeling as not just a means to building systems or creating data, but as a method that drive important dialogues in our community. Our conceptual models are expressions of our selves and our communities, and we need to build the tools that will allow us to reflect on them in meaningful ways.

Wickett’s Fundamental Questions of conceptual modeling in information science were described:

- **Questions of Definition and Description:** These questions are centered around how objects, texts, persons, events, concepts, and contexts are to be represented. By what features do we identify the members of some class of things? What features should be recorded to create representations of those things?
- **Questions of Order and Level:** Knowledge representation researchers have long argued for languages that operate at the “knowledge level”. Is the same approach appropriate for digital library development? Is first-order logic sufficient to encode our cultural knowledge, as might be supposed by the definitions given for the Resource Description Framework (RDF), or are second-order languages necessary?
- **Questions of Interaction and Use:** Conceptual modeling in information science is driven by the anticipated uses and interactions around our descriptive data. We must query our models not just for they represent things, but for how they encode and express uses of that data. Can we identify the ways that assumptions about audiences have informed our conceptual models?

3 Presentations

The following sections provide a summary of the paper presentations at SIG-CM 2019. Extended abstracts are available at the workshop archive (<https://github.com/sig-cm/JCDL2019>).

3.1 Practical and meta challenges in modeling database migrations: A case study of the MBGNA

Andrea K. Thomer, Samuel Sciolla, Kathryn Topham, Alexandria Rayburn & Maryse Lundering-Timpano.

Andrea Thomer presented a paper describing emergent work out of the “Migrating Research Data Collections” project, in which she and her team are studying the reasons for, and roadblocks to, database migration Andrea K. Thomer, Samuel Sciolla, Kathryn Topham, Alexandria Rayburn, and Maryse Lundering-Timpano (2019). In developing case studies of database and digital collection migration in natural history museum, they have found that there is a need for conceptual modeling support for information professionals in the midst of a migration, and for those wishing to document database migrations for other reasons. They discussed three ways of modeling changes to database over time: narrative case reports, similar to READMEs; versioned Entity-Relationship Diagrams; and Sankey diagrams showing information flows between systems over time. Each of these approaches may be adoptable by information professionals working with digital collections, though more work is needed to develop clear best practices for using each.

3.2 Reconstituting a Digital Repository through Use Case Driven Ontology Development

Adam Shepherd, Danie Kinkade, Douglas Fils.

Adam Shepherd presented work conducted with the Biological and Chemical Oceanography and Data Management Office (BCO-DMO), which manages data resulting from NSF core programs for Biological and Chemical Oceanography and the Office of Polar Programs Adam Shepherd, Danie Kinkade, and Douglas Fils (2019). BCO-DMO recently rearchitected its data infrastructure with a focus on its conceptual model, with the goal of simplifying software management and making logical assumptions within the software explicit in the data model. With its schema and axioms, the ontology would serve as the backbone to a knowledge graph that would drive the functions and capabilities across BCO-DMO’s software stack. BCO-DMO assembled a small team of experts to apply the Semantic Web Methodology and redesign the BCO-DMO data infrastructure and publish a new version of its Ocean Data Ontology.

3.3 Matryoshka Modeling: Building One Conceptual Model within Another

Michael R. Gryk

Michael R. Gryk presented a paper describing his ongoing research into data provenance, and in particular the tradeoffs of using different conceptual models for recording provenance in scientific workflows Michael R. Gryk (2019). The use case for this initial comparison of different conceptual modeling techniques is Biological Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (bioNMR). Gryk argued that PREMIS, a digital preservation data model, provided a “nesting” capability through its top level entities - Objects, Events, and Agents. This design affords the recording of, for example, three separate but simultaneous data collection Events in BioNMR. Ultimately, the conclusion of this work comes down to a tradeoff of many modeling exercises: The need for conceptual abstractions that are *useful* to different applications vs the need for tractable entities that can help *correctly* identify entities of a specific domain. Gryk ultimately argues that nested modeling can promote wider adoption by using robust, well-established conceptual models from other domains. However, it draws into contrast the usefulness of the model versus its correctness.

3.4 How to organize and reveal knowledge of cultural heritage digital resources? - A case study of Dunhuang Grottoes

Xiaoguang Wang; Wanli Chang; Hongyu Wang

Hongyu Wang presented on an attribute graph-based model for representing cultural heritage materials, in the context of the Dunhuang Grottoes project Xiaoguang Wang, Wanli Chang, and Hongyu Wang (2019). Dunhuang Grottoes is preserving a series of culturally significant paintings in 492 caves, while seeking to make the materials accessible and discoverable. Wang, Chang, and Wang describe insufficiencies in meeting these goals through regular RDF, which limits how certain characteristics and relationships are represented. As an alternative, they present a knowledge graph model centered on Cave, Component, and Object entities. The knowledge graph enables structured knowledge to be flexibly and precisely extracted; in turn improving tools for leveraging the Knowledge Graph for discovery. Wang demonstrated one example in the TDSAT (Text Deep Semantic Annotation Tool), which allows for complex retrieval - for example, noting that “Sakyamuni” and “Tathagata” refer to the same entity.

3.5 When Conceptual Models Collide: Aggregates in IFLA’s Library Reference Model

Jacob Jett and David Dubin

Jacob Jett presented on conceptual issues related to the WEMI entities in FRBR and updated in the IFLA LRM (Library Reference Model) conceptual model Jacob Jett and David Dubin (2019). WEMI, or work-expression-manifestation-item, present a way of representing entities. Jett and Dubin note issues in how LRM defines them. While the conceptual relationship has usually been top-down - i.e. an abstract work is realized through one or more expressions, each expression is embodied through one or more artifacts as a manifestation, and individual exemplars of manifestation are items - LRM introduces a bottom-up definition of a manifestation as an entity represented by attributes observed in items. Such

a definition presents a cardinality problem in many circumstances, Jett and Dubin note. For example, a copy of an issue of a journal or serial will exist in multiple sets - there may be multiple works in the issues, but if the manifestations inherit from the items, doing so both violates set theory and presents overly complex mixes of top-down and bottom-up relationships in WEMI.

4 Open Questions in Conceptual Modeling Research

During the workshop's open discussion period we sought to collectively identify themes from the workshop papers and discussions, along with corresponding open research questions relevant to conceptual modeling, knowledge organization and representation, as well as Information Science more generally. We have organized a review of the open discussion into approximately 30 research questions, within three overarching themes: (1) Modeling concepts; (2) Data concepts; (3) Infrastructure and Implementation.

4.1 Modeling concepts

Questions in this category relate to the process of creating, evaluating, critiquing or otherwise reviewing a conceptual model.

- How can we identify and distinguish closely related conceptual models or data models? For example, can we identify models in the same domain that are differentiated by level of representation or by semantic or functional goals? Or, from the opposite direction, can we identify models with closely related or intersecting purposes in different domains?
- How can we understand and express relationships among different but related conceptual and data models? What are the potential benefits of comparison, contrast, translation or crosswalking, or other formalizations of relationships among different conceptual or data models? Knowing that "all models are wrong", how do we understand the relationship between models that implement conflicting or complementary perspectives on data or knowledge in a domain? Or, for example, how do we understand the differences among and implications of models (ontologies) intended to support reasoning and inference, as opposed to support information organization?
- Can we identify, characterize, or formalize common relationships among different models and relevant software, tools, and data in different repositories?
- Can we identify, characterize, or formalize common relationships among different models, modeling languages, and standards?
- How can we best characterize, document, or formalize modeling decisions in different contexts, especially in light of the fact that all modeling choices are interpretive no model offers a universally "right" answer?

- How do we anticipate and characterize the consequences of modeling decisions, including dangerous patterns?
- How do we characterize, anticipate, and formalize modeling “errors” across domains, such logical inconsistencies, Type I vs. Type II errors, or instance vs. class errors, or modeling in such complexity that the model is as big as the domain it’s modeling (Borges’ error)?
- Can we establish a useful typology of information models, and situate conceptual models (of various types and kinds) within this typology? Further, what characteristics, properties, or features would usefully differentiate “types” of conceptual models?

4.2 Data concepts

Questions in this category refer to the definition and modeling of concepts related to data and datasets.

- What are datasets in different domains and contexts?
- How do we understand and formalize identity for datasets over time?
- How do we characterize and express relationships among different versions of data, including datasets at different levels of processing (“raw” vs. “cooked” data) and with varying serializations, or levels of granularity of expression (e.g., a file containing multiple datasets vs. the same dataset containing multiple files)?
- How do we characterize, teach, and address issues of language and ambiguity in modeling and data work, such as the distinction among mathematical integers vs. database integers, or language changes?
- How do we understand and formalize appropriate levels of granularity for the addressability of data and digital objects, to support different research communities, and different research questions or approaches?
- Can we identify and characterize common relationships among data and relevant software? For example, how is semantic information variously encoded or embedded into software and its functionality as opposed to modeled data used by the software, and what are the implications for communities of use? How do we characterize the differential robustness of data as opposed to software, and how do we influence communities of use in making decisions about data and software development?

4.3 Infrastructure and implementation

Questions in this category relate to the relationship between conceptual models and the infrastructure on which they are implemented; and to other issues related to the implementation and application of a model to a domain, problem, tool, or piece of software.

- How can we most effectively present or represent models to users in different contexts? And how do we understand relationships between models and their presentation or representation for users?
- How can we balance correctness versus usefulness in the development and implementation of conceptual models?
- When and how do models become infrastructure?
- What are lifecycle considerations in conceptual modeling?
- How can we continue to identify and advance best practices for understanding and evaluating the success of conceptual models (e.g., competency questions for ontologies)?
- How do we characterize the mutual impact of different factors in the implementation of conceptual models—models themselves, their usage and application, and system affordances—on one another, to historicize model development?
- Can we identify, historicize, and learn from exemplary cases of model development, evolution, or adoption, and where has this been done already?
- How do we understand the various roles and workflows involved in data modeling in different domains: Who is doing this work, and how?

5 Future work

The Special Interest Group on Conceptual Modeling (SIG CM) aims to be an inclusive intellectual community of researchers and practitioners interested in information modeling, data representation, and infrastructure design. As we saw at the SIG-CM workshop, work on these issues is happening across sub-domains of Information Science, including knowledge organization and representation, systems analysis and design, data curation and management, and conceptual modeling. By establishing SIG CM as a way to connect scholars across these areas of interest we hope that those areas can continue to exist, grow, and strengthen together.

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